

An Analysis of Access, Completion, and Academic Success in TESDA Diploma Programs in Tourism and Hospitality in Negros Oriental

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Article Details:

Received: 29 April 2026

Revised: 3 May 2026

Accepted: 11 May 2026

Published: 31 May 2026

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Recommended Citation:

Credo, V. C. Jr. (2026). An Analysis of Access, Completion, and Academic Success in TESDA Diploma Programs in Tourism and Hospitality in Negros Oriental. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*. 1 (6), 571-587.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20513816>

Index Terms:

administrative support, community support, financial strain, front office service, TESDA program

Abstract. This study investigated students' experiences in accessing and completing TESDA diploma programs and examined their relationship to academic success. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study utilized stratified random sampling to select 280 TESDA diploma students. Data were collected through validated questionnaires and analyzed using percentage, mean, and Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation. The findings revealed that the majority of respondents were female and in early adulthood. Overall, the students reported favorable experiences in both accessing and completing TESDA programs. Access-related factors were consistently rated high to very high, with family support and information awareness emerging as the strongest contributors. Other factors, such as geographical accessibility, academic preparedness, and community support, were also positively perceived, which stressed the importance of both personal and environmental influences in facilitating program entry. Similarly, completion-related factors reflected positive experiences, with administrative policies receiving the highest ratings, followed by responsibilities and financial considerations, suggesting that institutional structures play a critical role in sustaining student engagement. In terms of academic performance, students demonstrated achievement ranging from average to very good across TVET areas, with Front Office Services obtaining the highest mean score. Statistical analysis confirmed a significant relationship ($p < .05$) between students' experiences and academic performance, indicating that more positive access and completion experiences are associated with stronger academic outcomes. Based on these findings, it is recommended that TESDA and partner institutions continue to strengthen information dissemination, family engagement, and support systems, while also implementing targeted academic interventions to enhance student competencies, particularly in areas where lower performance is observed.

Introduction

Global initiatives continue to expand Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET). However, many countries still struggle with ensuring student access and completion. According to UNESCO (2022), factors such as geographic inaccessibility, lack of awareness, financial constraints, and inadequate academic preparedness affect individuals' ability to enroll in and complete TVET programs. In China, dropout rates among upper-secondary TVET students have reached 10.7%, rising to 22% in poorer inland regions due to financial difficulties and limited institutional support (Yi et al., 2015). Similarly, in Guyana, a 2024 workforce assessment revealed high attrition rates, with many students failing to complete certification requirements and 42% of exam takers failing to pass (Guyana Standard, 2024).

In the Philippines, TVET programs are vital for workforce development, yet students encounter significant factors affecting access and completion. Despite TESDA's government-funded scholarships, financial strain beyond subsidies, lack of awareness, and geographical inaccessibility persist. A report by the Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM II, 2025) highlighted extremely low completion rates in certain scholarship allocations in the National Capital Region, where only a small proportion of enrollees were able to complete the program. Although this reflects a specific

context rather than the entire TVET system, it underscores issues in student retention and program completion. On a similar note, the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS, 2024) has identified curriculum misalignment with industry demands, leading to skill gaps and employment difficulties.

At the regional level, similar concerns are evident in Region VII, particularly in Negros Oriental, where access to and completion of TESDA diploma programs are influenced by socio-economic and institutional factors. Despite national efforts to expand TVET participation, recent reports highlight persistent issues related to financial constraints, limited awareness, and inadequate support systems that affect student engagement and completion (Orbeta & Corpus, 2024). Evidence from local contexts further suggests that financial assistance and institutional support remain critical in enabling students to persist in their training, indicating that these conditions significantly influence participation and completion (Tilos, 2024).

Although several studies have examined TVET implementation, there remains a need for deeper understanding of the factors affecting access and completion in TESDA's three-year diploma programs. Previous research has focused on curriculum misalignment, faculty training, and industry partnerships, yet there is limited data on the socio-economic influences on student participation. In Negros Oriental, additional costs affect student completion, and local institutions like Metro Dumaguete College (MDC) face challenges in aligning TVET curricula with industry needs, resulting in limited employment opportunities (Metro Post, 2024). Moreover, low participation in TESDA's skills competitions, with only five TVIs joining in 2022, further highlights gaps in student engagement and training effectiveness (Lomotan, 2023).

Given these gaps, this study aims to investigate students' experiences in accessing and completing TESDA diploma programs in the tourism and hospitality industry in Negros Oriental and to determine how these experiences relate to their academic performance. Specifically, it examines key access factors such as geographical accessibility, information awareness, academic preparedness, family support, and community support, as well as completion factors including financial strain, personal and academic responsibilities, and administrative policies. By analyzing the relationship between these factors and students' academic performance in TESDA-aligned courses, this study seeks to provide a more comprehensive understanding of student experiences in TVET programs. The findings are expected to inform policy enhancements, strengthen support mechanisms, and contribute to improving student success in TVET programs. Furthermore, this study supports the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 on Quality Education, particularly Target 4.3, which promotes equal access to affordable and quality technical and vocational education.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to investigate students' experiences in accessing and completing TESDA diploma programs and how these experiences relate to student performance.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. diploma program?
2. To what extent do students experience the following factors in accessing the TESDA diploma program:
 - 2.1 geographical accessibility;
 - 2.2 information awareness;
 - 2.3 academic preparedness/prior skills alignment;
 - 2.4 family support;
 - 2.5 community support?
3. To what extent do students experience the following factors in completing the TESDA diploma program:
 - 3.1 financial strain (cost beyond subsidy);
 - 3.2 responsibilities (personal, school); and
 - 3.3 administrative policies (schedules, resources, etc.)?
4. What are the students' academic performance in the following subjects, with embedded TVET Resultant Qualifications:
 - 4.1 Housekeeping (Housekeeping NC II);
 - 4.2 Food and Beverage Services (Food and Beverage Services NC II); and
 - 4.3 Front Office Services (Front Office Services NC II)?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the students' experiences in accessing and completing the TESDA diploma program and their academic performance?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design. It is descriptive in nature because it identifies the students' experiences in accessing and completing TESDA diploma programs and assesses their academic success in selected technical subjects. It describes these variables in terms of geographical accessibility, information awareness, academic preparedness, family and community support, financial conditions, personal and academic responsibilities, and administrative policies. The study is also correlational in nature because it determines the relationship between students' experiences in access and completion and their academic success in TESDA diploma programs.

Research Environment

This study was conducted in the province of Negros Oriental, particularly in selected Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) offering three-year TESDA diploma programs. The province, located in Region VII (Central Visayas), hosts several TESDA-accredited institutions that provide competency-based training aligned with national standards and industry needs.

Among the recognized TVIs offering three-year diploma programs are Foundation University, Metro Dumaguete College, Teamskills Technological Institute, and Asian College. However, Foundation University was not included in this study as it primarily offers diploma programs related to agriculture, which are outside the scope of tourism and hospitality-focused programs. The participating institutions offer diploma programs designed to develop students' competencies in areas such as housekeeping, food and beverage services, and front office operations. These programs aim to prepare students for employment in tourism and hospitality industry, contributing to local workforce development.

Negros Oriental was selected as the research environment due to the presence of institutions offering TESDA diploma programs and the relevance of these programs in supporting skills development and employment opportunities in the province. This setting provides an appropriate context for examining students' experiences in access, completion, and academic success in TVET.

Research respondents

The respondents of this study were third-year TESDA diploma program students in the tourism and hospitality field in Negros Oriental. The technical subjects included in the study, namely Housekeeping, Food and Beverage Services, and Front Office Services, were selected as these are common across the three-year diploma programs and have embedded NC II certifications.

From a total population of 752 students enrolled in the identified diploma programs, the sample size was determined using Yamane's formula, resulting in 280 respondents. The respondents were selected through stratified random sampling based on diploma programs, namely Diploma in Tourism Technology (DTOT) of Metro Dumaguete College, Diploma in Tourism Technology (DTT) of Teamskills Technological Institute, and Diploma in Hotel and Restaurant Technology (DHRT) of Teamskills Technological Institute. The selection of respondents was conducted with the assistance of the program chairs of the respective institutions.

The sample size of 280 respondents was considered adequate to represent the population of third-year diploma students in the selected programs and to support the statistical analyses used in the study.

Research instruments

This study utilized a structured survey questionnaire as the primary research instrument to gather data. The questionnaire was designed to fit diverse perspectives into predetermined response categories, ensuring consistency in data collection. It includes closed-ended questions to quantify responses and facilitate easy comparison, summarization, and generalization of results.

Furthermore, the questionnaire was validated by at least three experts in the field of TVET and TESDA. It also underwent a dry run with 30 students to assess the reliability of the items using Cronbach's Alpha Test. The results show that all values surpass the 0.70 benchmark, confirming that the items in every variable possess adequate reliability.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed ethical research standards to ensure the safety, confidentiality, and voluntary participation of all respondents. Before data collection, the respondents were informed about the study's purpose and provided with an informed consent form. Their responses remained anonymous and confidential, and the data were used solely for academic purposes. Additionally, the participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any consequences. The study also adhered to TESDA guidelines and institutional ethical protocols to maintain integrity and respect for the rights of the respondents.

In compliance with the provisions of Republic Act No. 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher ensured that the collection and handling of academic performance data did not compromise the identity of the respondents. A formal request letter was submitted to the Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) where the study was conducted to obtain the necessary subject grades relevant to the research. The participating institutions provided a signed acknowledgment confirming that all student identifiers were removed and replaced with coded data prior to release. This measure ensured that no personally identifiable information was disclosed to the researcher, thereby safeguarding the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents throughout the data collection and analysis process.

Additionally, the researcher declared that GPT-3 and Grammarly were used to improve the clarity and readability of the manuscript. Following their use, the author thoroughly reviewed and revised the document and assumes full responsibility for its final content.

Research procedure

A formal request to conduct the research was then submitted to the presidents or authorized representatives of the TVIs offering the TESDA three-year diploma programs, duly endorsed by the Dean of the Graduate School of Foundation University. Of the identified institutions, only those that granted approval for the conduct of the study were included in the data collection process. Once approved, the request was forwarded to the program chairpersons and subsequently to the designated instructors of the student respondents.

During the administration of the questionnaires, the researcher explained the purpose and significance of the study to the participants. The completed questionnaires were collected immediately after the respondents finished answering them.

The researcher secured the official grades on selected subjects from the respective registrars of the TVIs. In compliance with Republic Act No. 10173, otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all retrieved academic records were anonymized prior to release and were handled with strict confidentiality throughout the study.

Finally, the data were organized using MS Excel, analyzed using JAMOVI software, and interpreted accordingly.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The data gathered in this study were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The percent was used to show how a part is related to a whole. It was employed in presenting the performance of the students in Housekeeping, Food and Beverage Services, and Front Office Services. The mean was employed to identify the extent to which students experienced the (a) challenges in accessing the TESDA program, (b) challenges in completing the TESDA program, and (c) extent of performance of the students. The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was utilized in finding the degree of relationship between the challenges in completion of the TESDA program of the students and their performance.

The following interpretations were also applied by the researcher to describe the challenges of the students:

Score	Verbal Description	Extent of Experience
5	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	Agree	High
3	Moderately Agree	Moderate
2	Disagree	Low
1	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered from the respondents. The results are organized in a logical sequence based on the stated research problems, with the findings displayed in both tabular and narrative forms. This structure ensures a clear and coherent presentation of the evidence needed to address each objective of the study.

Age	Frequency	Percent	Minimum	Maximum
20	46	16.43		
21	91	32.50		
22	62	22.15	20	42
23	37	13.21		
≥24	44	15.71		
Total	280	100		

Table 1. Profile of the Students in Terms of Age

Table 1 shows that the majority of the students are within the age range of 21 (32.50%) and 22 (22.15%), followed by those aged 20 (16.43%), ≥24 (15.71%), and 23 (13.21%), with an overall age range from 20 to 42 years. This indicates that most of the respondents are within the typical age of post-secondary learners, although the presence of older students suggests that TESDA diploma programs also attract non-traditional learners.

This finding supports the literature of Perater and Paglinawan (2025), which emphasized that TVET institutions often cater to a diverse age group, including individuals transitioning from the workforce or returning to education. However, the inclusion of older learners may also imply varying levels of academic preparedness and study habits, which can influence performance and completion. Lorenzo (2025) further noted that non-traditional students often face challenges in balancing academic responsibilities with work or family obligations, which may affect their persistence in the program. Thus, while the age diversity reflects inclusivity in TESDA programs, it may also necessitate differentiated support mechanisms to address varied learner needs.

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	89	31.79
Female	191	68.21
Total	280	100

Table 2. Profile of the Students in Terms of Sex

Table 2 reveals that the majority of the respondents are female (68.21%), while males comprise only 31.79% of the sample. This indicates a female-dominated participation in the TESDA diploma programs included in the study. This finding is consistent with Talento et al. (2022), who observed that female learners tend to enroll more in TVET programs, particularly in sectors such as hospitality, garments, and service-related fields. The dominance of female students may reflect gendered preferences and societal expectations that influence program choice.

Sex	Frequency	Percent
3-Year Diploma Program in Tourism Technology (DTT)	86	30.71
3-Year Diploma Program in Tourism Technology (DTOT)	96	34.29
3-Year Diploma Program in Hotel and Restaurant Technology (DHRT)	98	35.00
Total	280	100

Table 3. Profile of the Students in Terms of Diploma Program

Table 3 indicates that students are relatively evenly distributed across the three diploma programs, with the highest proportion enrolled in the 3-Year Diploma Program in Hotel and Restaurant Technology (35.00%), followed by Tourism Technology (34.29%), and another Tourism-related program (30.71%). This balanced distribution suggests that there is consistent interest across the offered specializations, particularly in hospitality and tourism-related fields. This trend aligns

with the Second Congressional Commission on Education (2025), which showed that programs in hospitality and tourism remain among the most in-demand due to their alignment with industry needs and employment opportunities.

However, despite strong enrollment, a press release by the PIDS (2024) and Orbeta and Corpus (2024) raised concerns about curriculum misalignment and skill gaps, which may limit graduates' employability. The relatively equal distribution of students across programs may indicate accessibility and availability of these courses, yet it does not necessarily guarantee successful completion or employment outcomes. Hence, while the findings support the popularity and relevance of these programs, they also reinforce the need to ensure that curriculum delivery and industry alignment are effectively implemented to maximize student success.

	Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1.	I find that the TESDA training center is accessible from my residence.	4.26	SA	VH	0.78
2.	I find that the distance to the training center does not hinder my application.	4.12	A	H	0.83
3.	I find that transportation costs do not prevent me from pursuing the scholarship.	4.11	A	H	0.88
4.	I find that I can easily travel to the training center for document processing.	4.10	A	H	0.86
5.	I find that transportation to the training venue is convenient for me.	4.06	A	H	0.89
6.	I find that my locality provides transportation options that support my scholarship application activities.	3.61	A	H	1.22
Composite		4.04	A	H	0.91

Table 4. Extent of Students' Experience in Accessing the TESDA Program in Terms of Geographical Accessibility

Table 4 presents the extent of students' experience in accessing the TESDA program in terms of geographical accessibility, with emphasis on how location, distance, and transportation factors influence students' ability to engage with the program.

Among the indicators, the highest mean is recorded for accessibility from residence ($\bar{x} = 4.26$), interpreted as a very high extent of experience. This suggests that students generally perceive TESDA training centers as physically reachable from where they live, indicating that location is not a major barrier for most respondents. A very high extent of experience in this aspect implies that proximity supports participation and encourages application to the program. This finding aligns with Benz (2025), who posited that closer proximity to educational institutions significantly increases students' likelihood of enrollment and participation. It connotes that when training centers are within reasonable reach, students are more motivated and capable of engaging in TVET programs.

The remaining indicators fall under a high extent of experience, beginning with distance not being a hindrance ($\bar{x} = 4.12$), followed closely by transportation costs ($\bar{x} = 4.11$), ease of travel for document processing ($\bar{x} = 4.10$), and transportation convenience ($\bar{x} = 4.06$). These results indicate that although students recognize some challenges related to distance and transportation, these factors generally do not significantly obstruct their participation. A high extent of experience suggests that students are still able to manage these logistical concerns, possibly due to available transport options or manageable travel expenses.

These findings are supported by Chua (2025), who noted that while transportation and related costs may pose challenges, they are not always prohibitive when support systems or accessible options are present. Similarly, Edralin and Pastrana (2023) claimed that improved access mechanisms and infrastructure can mitigate geographical constraints and promote participation.

The lowest mean among the indicators is availability of transportation options in the locality ($\bar{x} = 3.61$), which is still interpreted as a high extent of experience but is comparatively lower than the others. This suggests that while students generally have access to transportation, the availability and reliability of such options may not be as strong or consistent. This relatively lower rating implies potential gaps in local transport systems that could affect ease of access, particularly for students in more remote or underserved areas. This finding is consistent with UNESCO (2022), which identified geographic inaccessibility and limited transportation infrastructure as persistent barriers to education access, especially in rural communities. It also supports the observation of Chua (2025) that disparities in local resources can influence students' ability to fully engage in training opportunities.

The composite means of 4.04 indicates a high extent of experience in terms of geographical accessibility. This signifies that, in general, students perceive location and transportation factors as manageable and not major obstacles to accessing TESDA programs. The result implies that while minor challenges exist, geographical accessibility is relatively favorable among the respondents. Correspondingly, Orbeta and Corpus (2024) acknowledged that although geographic barriers remain a

concern in some areas, improvements in access and infrastructure have helped reduce their overall impact on TVET participation.

Indicators		\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1.	I find that information about TESDA scholarship opportunities is clear and available to me.	4.47	SA	VH	0.72
2.	I find that scholarship requirements are well-explained and easy to understand.	4.36	SA	VH	0.81
3.	I find that application instructions are complete and easy to follow.	4.32	SA	VH	0.77
4.	I find that scholarship announcements are timely and accessible.	4.27	SA	VH	0.79
5.	I find that I know where to obtain accurate information about TESDA scholarships.	4.23	SA	VH	0.78
6.	I find that the benefits and coverage of the scholarship are clearly communicated.	4.20	A	H	0.86
Composite		4.31	SA	VH	0.79

Table 5. Extent of Students' Experience in Accessing the TESDA Program in Terms of Information Awareness

Table 5 presents the extent of experience of the students in accessing the TESDA program in terms of information awareness, focusing on how clearly and effectively scholarship-related information is communicated to students. Among the indicators, the highest mean is observed in clarity and availability of scholarship information ($\bar{x} = 4.47$), interpreted as a very high extent of experience. This indicates that students clearly perceive that information regarding TESDA scholarship opportunities is accessible and understandable. A very high extent of experience points to the fact that students are well-informed, which facilitates their ability to make decisions and participate in the program. This finding supports Edralin and Pastrana (2023), who posited that access to clear and readily available information significantly enhances student participation in educational programs.

This is followed by other indicators with a very high extent of experience, including well-explained requirements ($\bar{x} = 4.36$), easy-to-follow application instructions ($\bar{x} = 4.32$), timely announcements ($\bar{x} = 4.27$), and knowledge of where to obtain accurate information ($\bar{x} = 4.23$). These results show that students consistently experience clarity, organization, and accessibility in the dissemination of scholarship-related information. Such findings imply that TESDA's communication strategies are effective in guiding students throughout the application process, reducing confusion and uncertainty. This aligns with the statement of Chua (2025) that improving public information campaigns enhances awareness and promotes equitable access to programs. Furthermore, UNESCO (2022) emphasized that information accessibility is a key factor in reducing barriers to education, as informed individuals are more likely to participate and complete programs.

The lowest mean is recorded for clarity of benefits and coverage ($\bar{x} = 4.20$), which falls under a high extent of experience. Although still positive, this slightly lower rating suggests that some students may not fully understand the full scope of what the scholarship provides. This indicates a minor gap in communication, particularly in explaining financial coverage and benefits in detail. This finding is consistent with Chua (2025), who pointed out that while information may be available, it does not always fully capture the actual costs and benefits, leading to partial understanding among students.

The composite mean of 4.31 indicates a very high extent of experience in terms of information awareness. This shows that students generally perceive TESDA scholarship information as clear, accessible, and sufficient for application and participation. The result signifies that effective dissemination of information plays a crucial role in facilitating access to TVET programs. This finding is supported by the notion of Edralin and Pastrana (2023) and UNESCO (2022) that transparent and accessible information systems are essential in promoting inclusive and equitable access to education.

Indicators		\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1.	I find that I have the basic skills required for the TESDA program I chose.	4.37	SA	VH	0.71
2.	I find that I can understand the lessons and competencies required in the program.	4.26	SA	VH	0.73
3.	I find that I am academically confident to participate in the program.	4.21	SA	VH	0.77
4.	I find that my prior education helped me meet the program's expectations.	4.08	A	H	0.84
5.	I find that I have prior knowledge relevant to the technical course I selected.	4.06	A	H	0.89
6.	I find that my previous academic background prepared me for the training.	4.05	A	H	0.92
Composite		4.17	A	H	0.81

Table 6. Extent of Students' Experience in Accessing the TESDA Program in Terms of Academic Preparedness

Table 6 presents the extent of students' experience in accessing the TESDA program in terms of academic preparedness or prior skills alignment, focusing on how students perceive their readiness and ability to meet the academic and technical

demands of the program. Among the indicators, the highest mean is observed in possession of basic skills ($\bar{x} = 4.37$), interpreted as a very high extent of experience. This demonstrates that students strongly perceive themselves as possessing the foundational competencies required for their chosen TESDA programs. A very high extent of experience suggests that students feel equipped to begin training, which supports confidence and reduces entry barriers. This finding aligns with Wilson (2025), who asserted that strong foundational skills contribute significantly to students' readiness and success in post-secondary education.

This is followed by other indicators with a very high extent of experience, including understanding of lessons and competencies ($\bar{x} = 4.26$) and academic confidence ($\bar{x} = 4.21$). These results signify that students generally feel capable of comprehending program content and are confident in their ability to engage in learning activities. Such findings imply that students' self-efficacy and preparedness positively influence their participation in TESDA programs. This supports Mokher and Park-Gaghan (2025), who conjectured that academic preparedness plays a crucial role in students' ability to succeed in course requirements. Similarly, Perater and Paglinawan (2025) emphasized that both readiness and effective learning habits are essential for successful transition into technical and higher education programs.

The remaining indicators fall under a high extent of experience, starting with prior education meeting expectations ($\bar{x} = 4.08$), followed by relevant prior knowledge ($\bar{x} = 4.06$), and academic background preparation ($\bar{x} = 4.05$). These results indicate that while students generally recognize the contribution of their previous education, the alignment between prior learning and TESDA program requirements is slightly less pronounced compared to their perceived skills and confidence. A high extent of experience suggests that students are adequately prepared, but there may still be gaps in aligning prior academic experiences with the specific technical demands of the program.

Similarly, Wilson (2025) observed that students from varying educational backgrounds may experience differences in preparedness, affecting their academic performance. Salvador et al. (2022) likewise reported that gaps in academic preparation can influence student retention and success in TVET programs.

Generally, the composite mean of 4.17 indicates a high extent of experience in terms of academic preparedness or prior skills alignment. In other words, students generally feel ready and capable of meeting the academic and technical requirements of the program, although some areas of alignment with prior education may still need strengthening. This finding is supported by Mokher and Park-Gaghan (2025) and Perater and Paglinawan (2025), who postulated that adequate academic preparation is essential in ensuring student success and persistence in technical and vocational education.

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1. I find that my family allows me time and resources to complete scholarship requirements.	4.50	SA	VH	0.70
2. I find that my family supports me financially during the application process.	4.43	SA	VH	0.80
3. I find that my family believes in the value of TESDA training for my future.	4.42	SA	VH	0.72
4. I find that my family helps me manage responsibilities related to my application.	4.37	SA	VH	0.80
5. I find that my family encourages me to pursue the TESDA scholarship.	4.26	SA	VH	0.87
Composite	4.40	SA	VH	0.78

Table 7. Extent of Students' Experience in Accessing the TESDA Program in Terms of Family Support

Table 7 presents the extent of experience in accessing the TESDA program in terms of family support, highlighting how family involvement influences students' ability to pursue and complete scholarship requirements.

Among the indicators, the highest mean is observed in the provision of time and resources ($\bar{x} = 4.50$), interpreted as a very high extent of experience. This indicates that students strongly perceive that their families actively provide the necessary time and support to meet scholarship requirements. A very high extent of experience suggests that such support reduces external pressures and enables students to focus on their application and training. This coincides with Gil AJ et al. (2021), who believe that family support plays a crucial role in enhancing student engagement and participation in educational activities.

This is followed by other indicators with very high extent of experience, including financial support during application ($\bar{x} = 4.43$), belief in the value of TESDA training ($\bar{x} = 4.42$), assistance in managing responsibilities ($\bar{x} = 4.37$), and encouragement to pursue the scholarship ($\bar{x} = 4.26$). These results indicate that students consistently experience strong emotional, financial, and practical support from their families. Such findings imply that family involvement significantly motivates students and helps them overcome potential barriers related to finances and responsibilities. This strengthens the statement of Orbeta and Corpus (2024) that strong family support can mitigate financial burdens and increase the likelihood of student

participation and completion in TVET programs. Likewise, Du Toit-Brits, as cited in Mabulana (2025), maintained that supportive environments foster motivation, autonomy, and sustained engagement in learning. It is worth noting that all indicators fall under a very high extent of experience, and there are no indicators categorized under high or low levels. This suggests that family support is consistently strong across all measured aspects, which reflects its critical role in facilitating access to TESDA programs.

Synthesizing the findings, the composite mean of 4.40 indicates a very high extent of experience in terms of family support. This demonstrates that students generally receive substantial assistance and encouragement from their families, which positively influences their ability to access and participate in TESDA programs. This finding is supported by Gil AJ et al. (2021) and Du Toit-Brits, as cited in Mabulana (2025), who both emphasized that family involvement is a key factor in promoting student engagement, persistence, and success in educational pathways.

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1. I find that community programs encourage residents to avail themselves of TESDA training.	4.23	SA	VH	0.86
2. I find that community initiatives promote awareness of TESDA programs and scholarships	4.20	A	H	0.86
3. I find that my community provides helpful information about TESDA scholarship opportunities.	4.17	A	H	0.89
4. I find that local leaders support students applying for technical-vocational programs.	4.17	A	H	0.90
5. I find that community organizations offer guidance during the application process.	4.13	A	H	0.88
6. I find that my local government assists in processing required documents.	4.03	A	H	1.00
Composite	4.15	A	H	0.90

Table 8. Extent of Students' Experience in Accessing the TESDA Program in Terms of Community Support

Table 8 presents the extent of students' experience in accessing the TESDA program in terms of community support, with emphasis on how community structures, local leadership, and initiatives assist students in pursuing TESDA opportunities. Among the indicators, the highest mean is observed in community programs encouraging participation ($\bar{x} = 4.23$), interpreted as a very high extent of experience. This indicates that students strongly perceive that community-based programs actively motivate residents to avail themselves of TESDA training. A very high extent of experience suggests that community-driven efforts play a significant role in promoting engagement and participation in technical-vocational education. This finding corresponds with the claim of Du Toit-Brits, as cited in Mabulana (2025), that a supportive community environment fosters motivation and encourages learners to take ownership of their educational pursuits.

The remaining indicators fall under a high extent of experience, starting with promotion of awareness ($\bar{x} = 4.20$), followed by provision of helpful information ($\bar{x} = 4.17$), support from local leaders ($\bar{x} = 4.17$), guidance during application ($\bar{x} = 4.13$), and assistance in document processing ($\bar{x} = 4.03$). These results indicate that while community support is generally present, its impact is slightly less pronounced compared to direct encouragement from community programs. A high extent of experience suggests that students still benefit from community initiatives, but there may be inconsistencies in the level or quality of support provided. This implies that although communities contribute to awareness and assistance, there is still room for strengthening the coordination, accessibility, and responsiveness of services.

These findings align with Chua (2025), who noted that while communities play a role in disseminating information and providing support, gaps in awareness and access to accurate information persist. Similarly, Khairunnisa et al. (2025) argued that limited local empowerment and insufficient government focus can reduce the effectiveness of community-based support systems.

The lowest mean is observed in local government assistance in document processing ($\bar{x} = 4.03$), which, although still interpreted as a high extent of experience, suggests that this aspect of support is the least experienced among the indicators. This implies that bureaucratic processes or limited local government capacity may affect the efficiency of assistance provided to students. This finding is consistent with Chua (2025), who posited that administrative and systemic limitations at the local level can hinder smooth access to educational programs.

Notably, there are no indicators that fall under a low extent of experience, indicating that community support is generally present and favorable across all measured aspects.

Collectively, the composite mean of 4.15 indicates a high extent of experience in terms of community support. This conveys that student generally perceive their communities as supportive in facilitating access to TESDA programs, although the level of support varies across different aspects. This finding corresponds with Du Toit-Brits, as cited in Mabulana (2025),

and Khairunnisa et al. (2025), who emphasized that while community involvement is essential in promoting educational participation, strengthening local systems and support mechanisms is necessary to maximize its impact.

Indicators		\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1.	I find that financial issues do not prevent me from completing the program	4.04	A	H	0.94
2.	I find that scholarship allowances adequately support my living and training costs.	3.95	A	H	0.90
3.	I find that I can afford transportation and materials needed for program participation	3.95	A	H	0.86
4.	I find that I can manage incidental costs related to training and assessments.	3.86	A	H	0.98
5.	I find that I have sufficient financial resources to cover program-related expenses	3.78	A	H	0.92
Composite		3.91	A	H	0.92

Table 9. Extent of Students Experience in Completing the TESDA Program in Terms of Financial Strain

Table 9 presents the extent of students' experience in completing the TESDA program in terms of financial strain, which highlights how students manage financial demands related to training, allowances, and program-related expenses.

Among the indicators, the highest mean is observed in financial issues not preventing completion ($\bar{x} = 4.04$), interpreted as a high extent of experience. This shows that students generally perceive financial challenges as not a significant hindrance to their ability to complete the program. A high extent of experience suggests that while financial strain exists, students are still able to cope with these challenges and persist in their studies. This finding supports TESDA (2018), which acknowledges that although financial difficulties are a common barrier, students often find ways to continue through available support mechanisms and personal resourcefulness.

This is followed by adequacy of scholarship allowances ($\bar{x} = 3.95$) and affordability of transportation and materials ($\bar{x} = 3.95$), both interpreted as a high extent of experience. These results indicate that students generally find scholarship support and personal finances sufficient to meet basic training-related needs. However, the slightly lower mean scores suggest that while support is present, it may not fully cover all expenses. Correspondingly, Chua (2025) asserted that scholarship provisions often fall short of actual costs, requiring students to shoulder additional financial burdens.

Next is management of incidental costs ($\bar{x} = 3.86$), also under a high extent of experience. This suggests that students are able to handle extra or unexpected expenses related to training and assessments, though with some level of difficulty. This reflects the reality that incidental costs, while manageable, can still create pressure on students' financial capacity. This is supported by the statement of TESDA (2018) that hidden or additional costs can affect student engagement and completion.

The lowest mean is recorded in sufficiency of financial resources ($\bar{x} = 3.78$), still interpreted as a high extent of experience, but comparatively lower than the rest. This indicates that although students generally manage their finances, there are noticeable limitations in having enough resources to fully cover all program-related expenses. In other words, financial strain remains a concern, even if it does not entirely prevent completion. This finding is consistent with Chua (2025), who asserted that financial gaps persist despite existing scholarship support, affecting students' overall experience.

Notably, all indicators fall under a high extent of experience, and there are no indicators categorized as very high or low. This implies that financial strain is present but manageable, representing a little bit of a challenge rather than an extreme barrier.

Broadly speaking, the composite mean of 3.91 indicates a high extent of experience in terms of financial strain. This suggests that students are generally able to cope with financial demands and continue their training, although financial limitations remain evident. This finding is supported by TESDA (2018), stating that while financial assistance helps sustain participation, gaps in funding and rising costs continue to pose challenges to student completion in TVET programs.

Indicators		\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1.	I find that my current commitments do not hinder my ability to complete the program.	4.20	A	H	0.81
2.	I find that I have enough time to balance training and other obligations.	4.19	A	H	0.81
3.	I find that I can manage work or family duties alongside my training schedule.	4.15	A	H	0.85
4.	I find that I can meet program deadlines despite my other responsibilities.	4.14	A	H	0.82
5.	I find that my personal responsibilities do not interfere with program participation	4.10	A	H	0.79
Composite		4.16	A	H	0.82

Table 10. Extent of Students' Experience in Completing the TESDA Program in Terms of Responsibilities

Table 10 presents the extent of students' experience in completing the TESDA program in terms of responsibilities, focusing on how students manage their personal, family, and work-related obligations alongside their training. Among the indicators, the highest mean is observed in commitments not hindering completion ($\bar{x} = 4.20$), interpreted as a high extent of experience. This indicates that students generally perceive that their existing responsibilities do not significantly obstruct their ability to complete the program. A high extent of experience suggests that students are able to cope with multiple demands and remain committed to their training. This finding coincides with the notion of Lorenzo (2025) that although students face multiple obligations, effective time management enables them to persist in their academic pursuits.

This is closely followed by having enough time to balance obligations ($\bar{x} = 4.19$) and managing work or family duties ($\bar{x} = 4.15$), both interpreted as a high extent of experience. These results indicate that students are generally capable of balancing their training with other life responsibilities. This implies that while competing demands exist, students develop strategies to maintain equilibrium between academic and personal commitments. Similarly, Lorenzo (2025) posited that students often juggle multiple roles, and their ability to manage these responsibilities is crucial for program completion.

Next is meeting program deadlines ($\bar{x} = 4.14$), which also falls under a high extent of experience. This suggests that students are able to fulfill academic requirements despite competing responsibilities, reflecting discipline and time management skills. This is consistent with findings that structured schedules and clear expectations help students stay on track even when facing multiple obligations.

The lowest mean is observed in personal responsibilities not interfering with participation ($\bar{x} = 4.10$), still interpreted as a high extent of experience. This indicates that although students generally manage their responsibilities, there are instances where personal duties may slightly affect their participation. In other words, responsibilities remain a potential challenge, though not a major barrier. This finding supports Chua's (2025) assertion that students with multiple obligations, particularly working learners, may experience occasional conflicts between training schedules and personal responsibilities.

Remarkably, all indicators fall under a high extent of experience, with no indicators categorized as very high or low. This implies that responsibilities are present but manageable, reflecting a balanced yet demanding student experience.

The composite mean of 4.16 indicates a high extent of experience in terms of responsibilities. This suggests that students are generally capable of balancing their academic, work, and personal obligations while completing the TESDA program. This finding is supported by Lorenzo (2025) and Chua (2025), who both emphasized that while responsibilities can pose challenges, effective time management and support systems enable students to successfully navigate these demands and complete their training.

Indicators		\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1.	I find that the TESDA program requirements are clear and manageable	4.35	SA	VH	0.76
2.	I find that program policies support my successful completion.	4.35	SA	VH	0.74
3.	I find that administrative support is available when needed to complete the program.	4.30	SA	VH	0.78
4.	I find that the assessment procedures do not create unnecessary obstacles.	4.20	A	H	0.78
5.	I find that program deadlines and schedules are feasible for me.	4.14	A	H	0.77
Composite		4.27	SA	VH	0.77

Table 11. Extent of Students' Experience in Completing the TESDA Program in Terms of Administrative Policies

Table 11 presents the extent of students' experience in completing the TESDA program in terms of administrative policies, focusing on how institutional guidelines, procedures, and support systems influence students' ability to complete the program. Among the indicators examined, the highest means are observed in clarity and manageability of requirements and policies supporting completion (both $\bar{x} = 4.35$), interpreted as a very high extent of experience. These results indicate that students strongly perceive TESDA's requirements and policies as clear, organized, and supportive of their academic progress. A very high extent of experience suggests that well-structured policies reduce confusion and enable students to navigate program expectations effectively. This finding supports TESDA (2023), which stated that clearly defined competency-based systems and structured policies are essential in guiding students toward successful program completion.

This is followed by availability of administrative support ($\bar{x} = 4.30$), also interpreted as a very high extent of experience. This indicates that students perceive that assistance from administrators is readily accessible when needed, which enhances their ability to address concerns and complete requirements. Such findings imply that responsive administrative systems contribute significantly to student persistence. According to TESDA (2018), institutional support services play a crucial role in sustaining student engagement and completion in TVET programs.

The remaining indicators fall under a high extent of experience, beginning with assessment procedures not being obstacles ($\bar{x} = 4.20$), followed by the feasibility of deadlines and schedules ($\bar{x} = 4.14$). These results indicate that while students generally find assessment processes and schedules manageable, there are slight challenges in fully accommodating all learners' circumstances. A high extent of experience implies that these aspects are functional but may still require improvements to better suit diverse student needs. This finding is consistent with Chua (2025), who observed that administrative processes, while generally structured, can sometimes create minor difficulties due to rigid scheduling or procedural demands. Similarly, TESDA (2018) noted that inefficiencies in implementation and resource limitations may affect the overall effectiveness of program delivery.

Markedly, there are no indicators that fall under a low extent of experience, indicating that administrative policies are generally perceived positively by the students.

In general, the composite mean of 4.27 indicates a very high extent of experience in terms of administrative policies. This signifies that student view TESDA's policies, procedures, and support systems as highly effective in facilitating program completion. The result implies that strong institutional frameworks and administrative support play a vital role in ensuring student success. This finding is supported by TESDA (2018), which emphasized that well-designed policies and responsive administrative systems are key factors in improving student retention and completion in TVET programs.

Rating	Verbal Equivalent	Housekeeping		Food and Beverage		Front Office Services	
		f	%	f	%	f	%
94 – 100	Excellent	23	8.21	11	3.93	45	16.07
88 – 93	Very Good	103	36.79	50	17.86	96	34.29
84 – 87	Good	78	27.86	55	19.64	72	25.71
80 – 83	Average	54	19.29	90	32.14	48	17.14
76 – 79	Below Average	20	7.14	49	17.50	17	6.07
75	Passing	2	0.71	24	8.57	2	0.71
≤74	Failing	---	---	1	0.36	---	---
Total		280	100	280	100	280	100
Mean		86.46 (Good)		83.03 (Average)		87.50 (Very Good)	
SD		4.81		5.50		5.30	

Table 12. Performance of the Students in Subjects with imbedded TVET Resultant Qualifications

Table 12 presents the students' performance in subjects with embedded TVET resultant qualifications across three program areas: Housekeeping, Food and Beverage, and Front Office Services. The results indicate varying levels of academic performance among students, with Front Office Services obtaining the highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 87.50$), followed by Housekeeping ($\bar{x} = 86.46$), and Food and Beverage with the lowest mean ($\bar{x} = 83.03$). These findings suggest that while students generally demonstrate average to very good performance across all areas, there are notable differences in achievement depending on the specialization.

In Housekeeping, the majority of students fall within the "Very Good" (36.79%) and "Good" (27.86%) categories. This points to a generally solid level of competency and suggests that students are able to meet the required standards of the program, which may reflect effective curriculum delivery and alignment with student capabilities. However, the presence of students

in the lower performance brackets, such as “Below Average” (7.14%) and “Passing” (0.71%), implies that some learners may still struggle with the competencies required. This variation supports the finding of Jaukal (2022) that differences in access to instructional resources and challenges in curriculum implementation can influence student performance in TVET programs.

For Food and Beverage, student performance is more dispersed, with the largest proportion in the “Average” category (32.14%), followed by “Good” (19.64%), and “Very Good” (17.86%). Notably, this area also has a relatively higher percentage of students in the “Below Average” (17.50%) and “Passing” (8.57%) categories, as well as a small proportion failing (0.36%). This distribution indicates that students in this specialization may be encountering greater academic or practical challenges. Correspondingly, TESDA (2018) emphasized that inadequate training facilities and limited access to industry-standard equipment can negatively affect students’ acquisition of practical skills, particularly in hands-on fields like food and beverage services. Additionally, Lorenzo (2025) asserted that balancing academic responsibilities with other obligations may further impact student performance, which could explain the wider spread of scores.

In contrast, Front Office Services shows the highest performance among the three areas, with a high concentration of students in the “Excellent” (16.07%) and “Very Good” (34.29%) categories, and the highest overall mean. This suggests that students in this program are better able to meet or exceed expected competencies. One possible explanation is that the skills required in front office services, such as communication and customer interaction, may be more aligned with students’ existing abilities or may require fewer specialized resources compared to other technical areas. However, Orbeta and Corpus (2024) noted that TVET programs sometimes suffer from gaps in soft skills development. Thus, the strong performance in this area may indicate effective training in these competencies within the institution.

Collectively, the findings of Table 4 suggest that while students generally perform at an acceptable to high level in TVET-related subjects, disparities exist across program areas. These differences may be influenced by factors such as the availability of resources, alignment of curriculum with industry standards, and students’ academic preparedness. As supposed by Wilson (2025) and Mokher and Park-Gaghan (2025), students’ prior preparation and access to learning support significantly affect their academic success. Therefore, enhancing instructional resources, strengthening curriculum implementation, and providing targeted academic support may help improve performance, particularly in areas where students demonstrate lower achievement.

Overall academic performance of students and...	r_s	p	Remark
Factors in Accessing TESDA			
● Geographical Accessibility	.222	< .001	Significant
● Information Awareness	.176	.003	Significant
● Acad. Preparedness/Prior Skills Alignment	.218	< .001	Significant
● Family Support	.162	.007	Significant
● Community Support	.171	.004	Significant
● Overall	.229	< .001	Significant
Factors in Completing TESDA Program			
Financial Strain	.238	< .001	Significant
Responsibilities	.171	.004	Significant
Administrative Policies	.207	< .001	Significant
Overall	.234	< .001	Significant

Table 13. Experiences in Accessing and Completing the TESDA Program and the Academic Performance of Students

Table 13 presents the relationship between the students’ experiences in accessing and completing the TESDA program and their overall academic performance. The results reveal that all identified factors are significantly correlated with academic performance, as indicated by p-values less than 0.05. This suggests that the extent to which students positively experience access and completion conditions is significantly associated with their academic outcomes.

Within the set of indicators in accessing TESDA, geographical accessibility ($r_s = .222$, $p < .001$) shows a significant relationship with academic performance. This implies that students who experience better accessibility to training institutions tend to demonstrate improved academic outcomes. When students can easily reach training centers, they are

more likely to attend regularly and engage effectively in learning activities. This finding supports Benz (2025), who posited that proximity to educational institutions enhances participation and progression.

Similarly, information awareness ($r_s = .176$, $p = .003$) is significantly related to performance, indicating that students who experience clear and accessible information about program offerings and requirements are better positioned to succeed academically. This aligns with Edralin and Pastrana (2023) and Chua (2025), who noted that adequate awareness enhances access, engagement, and academic achievement.

Academic preparedness or prior skills alignment ($r_s = .218$, $p < .001$) also demonstrates a significant relationship with academic performance. This signifies that student who experience strong academic readiness and alignment of prior skills with program requirements tend to perform better. Adequate preparation enables students to understand lessons more effectively and meet competency standards. This finding is consistent with Wilson (2025) and Mokher and Park-Gaghan (2025), who postulated that strong academic preparation contributes to higher retention and academic success.

In addition, family support ($r_s = .162$, $p = .007$) and community support ($r_s = .171$, $p = .004$) both show significant associations with academic performance, emphasizing the importance of supportive environments in student success. These results support Gil Aj et al. (2021), who found that family support enhances student engagement, and Du Toit-Brits, as cited in Mabulana (2025), who emphasized that a supportive community fosters motivation and self-directed learning.

Generally, the combined factors in accessing TESDA ($r_s = .229$, $p < .001$) exhibit a significant relationship with academic performance, implying that positive access-related experiences collectively contribute to improved academic outcomes. This finding is consistent with Orbeta and Corpus (2024), who identified that enabling conditions such as accessibility, awareness, and support systems are critical determinants of student participation and success.

With respect to the factors in completing the TESDA program, financial capacity and support ($r_s = .238$, $p < .001$) show the strongest relationship with academic performance among all variables. This indicates that students who experience adequate financial support and are able to manage program-related expenses tend to achieve better academic performance. When financial concerns are minimized, students can focus more on their studies and training requirements. This supports the statements of Chua (2025) and TESDA (2018) that sufficient financial resources enhance student engagement and completion.

Responsibilities ($r_s = .171$, $p = .004$) also show a significant relationship, suggesting that students who are able to effectively manage their work, family, and personal obligations alongside training tend to perform better academically. This is consistent with Lorenzo (2025), who noted that effective management of multiple responsibilities supports academic success.

Administrative policies ($r_s = .207$, $p < .001$) are likewise significantly related to academic performance, indicating that students who experience clear, supportive, and well-implemented institutional processes are more likely to achieve better outcomes. Efficient administrative systems, including clear requirements and accessible support, facilitate smoother program completion. This finding aligns with Chua (2025), who highlighted the importance of organized systems and adequate resources, as well as TESDA (2018), which emphasized that effective institutional support enhances student learning and performance.

Generally, the factors in completing the TESDA program ($r_s = .234$, $p < .001$) demonstrate a significant relationship with academic performance, reinforcing the idea that positive completion-related experiences substantially contribute to students' academic success. These findings are consistent with Tinto's Model of Student Retention, which posits that academic and social integration, along with supportive conditions, significantly influence student persistence and performance (Tinto, 2024).

Conclusion and Recommendations

TESDA diploma students are generally well-positioned to successfully engage in and complete their programs due to the presence of supportive access conditions and enabling completion mechanisms. The strong levels of information awareness, family support, and administrative assistance indicate that students are provided with clear guidance and a stable support system, allowing them to navigate both entry and completion processes with confidence.

Moreover, students demonstrate the capacity to balance academic demands with personal and financial responsibilities, suggesting a level of adaptability and resilience necessary for sustained participation in technical-vocational education. While financial considerations remain present, they do not substantially hinder students' ability to persist, indicating that existing support structures are sufficient to maintain engagement.

In terms of academic performance, students exhibit the ability to understand, apply, and perform competencies required in their respective specializations. Their performance across subjects reflects not only knowledge acquisition but also the capability to translate learned skills into practical and authentic tasks, particularly in areas that align closely with their strengths.

Finally, the significant relationship between students' experiences and their academic performance affirms that positive learning environments, accessibility, preparedness, and support systems collectively contribute to student success. When students are provided with conducive conditions both in accessing and completing the program, they are more likely to achieve favorable academic outcomes and demonstrate competency in their chosen fields.

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, it is hereby recommended that:

1. TESDA and partner institutions sustain and further enhance information dissemination and support systems to ensure that students remain well-informed about TESDA programs, requirements, and opportunities, while also strengthening family engagement initiatives to maintain strong support for student participation.
2. TESDA should improve financial assistance and resource provision by increasing scholarship support, allowances, and access to necessary training materials to help students better manage program-related expenses and sustain their engagement.
3. TESDA and partner institutions should enhance geographical accessibility by strengthening the strategic placement of training delivery sites and expanding partnerships with accessible host institutions.
4. TESDA and LGUs consider support mechanisms such as transportation assistance or student mobility support to help learners from distant areas sustain participation in the three-year diploma program.
5. Partner institutions provide targeted academic support and competency-based interventions to strengthen students' skills and performance, particularly in areas where lower academic outcomes are observed.
6. TESDA and partner institutions sustain and continuously improve administrative policies and support services to maintain efficient processes, accessible assistance, and student-centered systems that facilitate smooth program completion and academic success.
7. Students actively manage their responsibilities and leverage available support systems by balancing personal, work, and academic obligations while taking full advantage of family, community, and institutional resources to enhance their learning outcomes and complete the three-year diploma programs.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the colleagues and institutions who provided guidance, feedback, and support throughout the conduct of this research and the preparation of this manuscript. Any remaining errors or omissions are the sole responsibility of the authors.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Benz, R. (2025). Geographical constraints and upper secondary track choice: does distance to schools prevent students from entering school-based programmes? *Review of Regional Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10037-025-00249-9>

- Chua, C. C. (2025). Rationalizing TVET provision and support for enhanced public-private complementarity. EDCOM II. Retrieved from: <https://edcom2.gov.ph/publications/rationalizing-tvet-provision-and-support-for-enhanced-public-private-complementarity/>
- Edralin, D., & Pastrana, R. (2023). Technical and vocational education and training in the Philippines: In retrospect and its future directions. *Bedan Research Journal*, 8(1), 138–172. <https://doi.org/10.58870/berj.v8i1.50>
- Gil, A. J., Antelm-Lanzat, A. M., Cacheiro-González, M. L., & Pérez-Navío, E. (2021). The effect of family support on student engagement: Towards the prevention of dropouts. *Psychology in the Schools*, 58(6), 1082–1095. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.22490>
- Guyana Standard. (2024, June 18). High dropout rates in Guyana's TVET sector underscore need for educational reforms – Report. Retrieved from <https://www.guyanastandard.com/2024/06/18/high-dropout-rates-in-guyanas-tvet-sector-underscore-need-for-educational-reforms-report/>
- Jaukal, J. M. (2022). Challenges on the Implementation of the 3-Year Diploma Curriculum in TESDA Region IX. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 4(1), 164–170. <https://doi.org/10.54476/iimrj20>
- Khairunnisa, P., Hanif, F. F., & Prasetyo, C. (2025). Distributed outreach for literacy and access: Efforts to bridge accessibility, availability, and awareness of quality education for underprivileged groups to support local empowering and community development. *Interaction Community Engagement and Social Environment*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.61511/icese.v2i2.2025.1436>
- Lomotan, R. A. (2023, May 18). TESDA, NOATI highlight advantages in joining TESDA Skills Competitions. Philippine Information Agency. Retrieved from <https://mirror.pia.gov.ph/news/2023/05/18/tesda-noati-highlight-advantages-in-joining-tesda-skills-competitions>
- Lorenzo, N. (2025). Implementation and Challenges of Diploma Programs: Insights from TESDA-Aparri Polytechnic Institute. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 3(8), 717–729. <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2025.491>
- Mabulana, K. (2025). Learners' preparedness for higher education in South Africa: developing a sense of academic belonging through the selective learning approach. *Frontiers in Education*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2025.1465786>
- Metro Post. (2024, August 18). Educating for jobs: The TVET challenge. Dumaguete MetroPost. Retrieved from <https://metropost-online.com/educating-for-jobs-the-tvet-challenge/>
- Mokher, C. G., & Park-Gaghan, T. J. (2025). How Academic Preparation Shapes College Students' Own Success and the Success of their Peers in Corequisite Courses: Evidence from Texas. *AERA Open*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23328584251385469>
- Orbeta, A., & Corpus, J. P. (2024). Issues in Philippine TVET: Responsiveness to Industry Demand and Barriers to Access among Disadvantaged Youth. In *Philippine Institute for Development Studies eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.62986/rps2024.03>
- Perater, A. E., & Paglinawan, J. L. (2025). Transitioning to Higher Education: An assessment on the readiness of Alternative Learning System (ALS) graduates pursuing bachelor's degree. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, IX(V), 2350–2360. <https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2025.905000183>
- Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS). (2024). Skills mismatch: A barrier to economic growth. PIDS Press Releases. Retrieved from <https://www.pids.gov.ph/details/news/press-releases/skills-mismatch-a-barrier-to-economic-growth>
- Salvador, R. Q., Borrromeo, C. M. T., Limon, M. R., Parinas, M. a. G., De La Cruz, L. L., & Dalere, J. M. B. (2022). Exploring Technical-Vocational Education Teachers' Challenges and Adaptation Strategies in Teaching Courses Outside their Specializations. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.30880/jtet.2022.14.02.004>
- Second Congressional Commission on Education. (2025, January 27). Fixing the foundations: A matter of national survival. EDCOM 2 Year Two Report. Retrieved from <https://edcom2.gov.ph/media/2025/01/EDCOM-2-Year-2-Report-Fixing-the-Foundations-2025.pdf>
- Talento, M. S., Tandang, N., Rogelio, R. A., & Araña-Roldan, R. A. (2022). Factors influencing employment of female graduates of technical and vocational education and training program in the Philippines. *The Philippine Journal of Science*, 151(3). <https://doi.org/10.56899/151.03.30>
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2018). National Technical Education and Skills Development Plan 2018–2022. https://sea-vet.net/images/seb/initiatives/appendix_file/577/ntesdpfinalwithcover-1.pdf
- Tilos, J. (2024, February 19). TESDA scholar proves financial constraint not a hindrance to education, employment. Philippine Information Agency. <https://pia.gov.ph/news/tesda-scholar-proves-financial-constraint-not-a-hindrance-to-education-employment/>
- Tinto, V. (1975). Dropout from Higher Education: A Theoretical Synthesis of Recent Research. *Review of Educational Research*, 45(1), 89. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1170024>
- UNESCO. (2022). Transforming Technical and Vocational Education and Training for Successful and Just Transitions: UNESCO Strategy 2022-2029. Retrieved from https://unevoc.unesco.org/pub/unesco_strategy_for_tvet_2022-2029.pdf
- Wilson, D. (2025). Academic Preparedness and Institutional Support for Low-Income Students: A Scoping Review of College Success and Retention. https://mavmatrix.uta.edu/socialwork_theses/221

Yi, H., Zhang, L., Yao, Y., Wang, A., Ma, Y., Shi, Y., Chu, J., Loyalka, P., & Rozelle, S. (2015). Exploring the dropout rates and causes of dropout in upper-secondary technical and vocational education and training (TVET) schools in China. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 42, 115–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2015.04.009>

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.